

An evaluation of online grammar checkers in the development of students' grammar skills: Basis for proposed instructional guidelines

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the role of online grammar checkers in the development of students' grammar skills and to propose instructional guidelines based on the results of the study. This research explored whether online grammar checkers can help learners develop their grammar skills. This study employed an experimental research design to see how well students can check their own grammar using and without online grammar checkers. Eighty-four (84) senior high school students from St. Dominic College of Asia are the respondents to this study, which was divided into experimental and control groups. The researchers formulated a survey questionnaire as the data gathering instrument, which was used to analyze and comprehend the responses gathered from the respondents. The results presented a relatively positive perception, where the majority of the students perceive that online grammar checkers have good qualities and can be useful in editing their written academic texts. This finding assumes that while the majority of the SHS students have a positive perception of using online grammar checkers, it also shows that a large proportion have a high proficiency in grammar since they can identify and fix grammar errors even without the use of online grammar checkers. However, although the difference in the control group is slightly higher than the experimental group, no significant difference has been identified between the control and experimental groups of students in terms of error rates.

Keywords: Online grammar checkers; Development; Grammar skills; Senior high school students.

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Introduction

Grammatical skills are critical to any form of writing since they help the writer express ideas clearly and accurately. Writing well and succeeding in academic settings require writers to adhere to accepted English grammar conventions, which include precise sentence structure, proper subject-verb agreement, consistent and appropriate tense usage, and the correct use of articles (Narita, 2012). Nonetheless, most students still have difficulty with writing, and they struggle to employ successful or precise language (Myhill et al., 2012).

This problem in grammar is mostly a burden for those who need to check the written documents, like the editors, proofreaders, and especially the advisers. Most paper advisers would agree that students' knowledge of grammar is always a main problem. The majority of them, however, are time-constrained and have a limited capacity for grammatical correction, despite research showing the beneficial effects of feedback on grammar. It is possible for advisers to believe that they are not accountable for offering students comprehensive grammatical input on their papers, or they may lack confidence in their ability to teach intricate grammatical rules (Jones et al., 2013). In the short time allotted for a student consultation, an adviser may not have the resources to give students thorough grammatical input, even if they are eager or able to do so. This is especially true if there are additional writing-related concerns that require the adviser's attention. As a result, more students—native and non-native English speakers alike—often require more assistance with proofreading and grammatical editing than the university is prepared or willing to provide (Cavaleri & Dianati, 2016).

Consequently, the limitation of student-adviser consultation became worse during the COVID-19 pandemic, when students could not personally visit people who could help them check their papers. Using self-access resources more often, such as grammar checkers available online, is one way to address this issue. Although grammar books and paper-based exercises are flexible, online grammar checkers offer direct student interaction that these materials cannot. Free or paid grammar checkers can automatically identify and offer corrections for grammatical mistakes in written work. Owing to advancements in artificial intelligence, algorithmic applications, and natural language processing, a number of grammar checkers on the market claim that they can provide students with insightful and useful feedback on their grammar, all the while supporting their self-regulation techniques.

Some of the online grammars that became popular are Grammarly, Ginger Software, QuillBot, SpellCheck Plus, and many more. These internet checkers offer the elimination of grammar mistakes, misspellings, inappropriate punctuation, sentence structure issues, and more. Based on the researchers' awareness, due to the online modality of education during the pandemic, students rely more on online checkers when checking their work instead of asking for help from a professional or their teachers.

Students also use online grammar checkers to easily produce outputs needed for their classes, which can cause deterioration in developing their grammar skills. According to Mozgovoy (2011), a grammar checker aids pupils in identifying grammatical problems in written work. When errors are made, such as when the subject-verb agreement, articles, or punctuation are misused, the program automatically detects them and gives feedback. A grammar checker can also find spelling mistakes in words. This tool highlights words that are misspelled or unclear. Hence, the researchers investigated the usage of online grammar tools in developing students' grammar skills and proposed instructional guidelines for future teachers.

Even though online grammar checkers were already in use prior to the pandemic, the implementation of grammar and spelling checkers for writing classes was not well received, particularly in the early 1990s. This was because grammar checkers at the time were only useful for identifying spelling or language mistakes rather than providing helpful feedback on the structure and content of essays. Users' negative opinions of the software in language classes were caused by the technical shortcomings of grammar checkers, which included imprecise feedback and a subpar error detection feature (Vernon, 2000). However, given their ongoing growth and practical application, grammar checkers' impact on students' writing skills must be evaluated.

With the health crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, the researchers have witnessed a noticeable utilization of online grammar tools during the emergence of online classes. Due to a great shift in the learning modality, this study was conducted to identify and evaluate the various online grammar tools currently used to help students correct their English grammar skills. Furthermore, researchers also aim to comprehend how frequently students use online grammar checkers in their academic writings, what grammar skills are addressed while using these checkers, and what are their perceptions towards their quality in helping develop the English grammar skills to propose instructional guidelines that will help future English teachers create an effective lesson plan in teaching English grammar.

To do this, the researchers conducted an experimental study among students who use and do not use online grammar tools to determine how these grammar tools help them correct a given text. Also, the researchers aim to identify the perceptions of the students about learning English grammar using these online tools and propose instructional guidelines that will help future English teachers create an effective lesson plan for teaching English grammar.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of this study is to evaluate online grammar checkers in the development of students' grammar skills. Therefore, the researchers came up with specific questions that this study aims to answer.

1. What is the level of perception of using online grammar checkers among Senior High School students?
2. What errors are detected in checking grammar in written texts?
3. Is there a significant difference between the control group and experimental group in terms of checking grammar in written texts?
4. What instructional guidelines can be proposed based on the result of this study?

Review of Related Literature

Pauta (2013) stated that English is the current and widely used international lingua franca. As the world becomes increasingly interconnected through new emerging technologies, the need to use the English language becomes more evident, and people from all around the world can now communicate more efficiently than at any other time in history. As a result of these technological advances, and similar to a person's competent use of technology, it has also become necessary to develop the skills of effective speaking or writing in English if one were to participate globally, especially as English is extensively utilized in different sectors such as business and education.

Learning the English language shifted mainly from traditional face-to-face learning to online learning. With this, Hidayat (2021) said that all of the tasks students typically complete in the classroom continue to be done even when the learning processes are carried out online. In this phase of the process, the only distinction is in how the learning is implemented—it is no longer done face-to-face but rather remotely. This has resulted in educational activities, including English language acquisition and related concepts such as grammar development, being done online. According to Bradshaw (2013), one of the core concepts of the English language is grammar. Grammar competency is a prerequisite for being able to communicate in any language, regardless of the language. Strong grammar instruction is associated with improved communication skills and a higher likelihood of being understood by others. Furthermore, having a strong understanding of grammar enables one to generate writing of outstanding quality.

This has resulted in countless programs that have been created to assist language learners in becoming more fluent in their chosen language due to the technology's rapid development. An innovative, effective, and powerful instrument for technology-enhanced learning is now available thanks to the Internet. Thus, grammar-correcting applications and websites have been reutilized, like Grammarly, Ginger Software, QuillBot, SpellCheck Plus, and many more. These online grammar tools offer the elimination of grammar mistakes, misspellings, inappropriate punctuation, sentence structure issues, and more.

Grammar

According to Richards and Schmidt (2010), grammar is a description of a language structure, and the way words and other linguistic units are combined to form sentences. In a similar manner, Huddleston et al. (2022) assert that grammar takes the form of shorter sentence units like words, sentences, and clauses. Moreover, Ur (1999) emphasized that grammar is defined as the arrangement of words to form correct sentences, as well as the meaning of such statements. Therefore, it can be said that grammar is a linguistic framework that functions to create words and sentences.

Grammatical Rules

DeKeyser (1998) pointed out that if learners have the opportunity to apply and practice what they have learned from several communicative engagements and activities, explicit knowledge of grammar is transformed into implicit knowledge. According to LeTourneau (2001), with the elements of sentence structure, one's understanding is most beneficial during the revision and editing phases.

Andriani et al. (2021) said that teaching English grammar rules needs context, as they are also applicable to our everyday lives. A crucial component of becoming an effective communicator is by learning grammar and its principles.

Grammatical Error

According to Hsu (2013), inaccurate forms, semantic meanings, and uses of the foreign language resulting from learners' inadequate comprehension of these norms form grammatical errors, which are variations from learners' application of certain language rules. With this, it can be claimed that grammar errors are inevitable when a student develops their proficiency with a language.

James (1998) said that morphological and syntactical faults are what are referred to as grammatical errors. He emphasized that whereas syntactical errors impact writings bigger than words, such as phrases, clauses, sentences, and paragraphs, morphological faults, on the other hand, include a failure to furnish any portion of word classes such as noun, verb, adjective, adverb, and preposition. In addition, Ellis (2017) also said that overgeneralization mistakes, transfer errors, and errors of omission are three types of errors.

Brown (2014) claimed that interlingual transfer, where the learner's native language serves as a reference; intralingual transfer, where the learner incorrectly generalizes rules with the target language; the context of learning, where a learner may make mistakes due to the context, such as false information and incorrect word presentation; and communication of strategies, or the learner's preferred learning style, are the four potential sources of error. With this, it can be said that each learner uses a different method of learning to improve their communication skills, but these methods can also lead to mistakes.

Grammar Skills and Competence of the Learners

Furtina et al. (2016) stated that before they may construct sentences in a foreign language, students must be familiar with the grammar rules of that language. This is so because students make use of grammatical rules to generate sentences that make sense (Erlangga et al., 2019). Likewise, Millrood (2014) proposed a theory where students need a set of theoretical knowledge and language skills to create correct sentences, recognize grammatical errors, and carry out language activities when studying grammar in the context of learning a foreign language. While, Mabuan (2015) said that first language interference and negative transfer from L1 to L2 may be to blame for the mistakes in tenses, verbs, prepositions, articles, pronouns, morphology, and subject-verb agreement made by students in their blog postings. These mistakes showed that even though students are aware that these forms exist in English grammar, they still struggle with them. The acquisition of a second language necessitates the development of grammar competence. Furthermore, Ferris (2004) asserts that grammar error correction is said to help adult learners recognize their mistakes and prevent mistakes from becoming fossilized, which in turn improves their linguistic proficiency. Ferris and Roberts (2001) said that students who got error feedback performed better in writing classes and showed stronger self-correction abilities than students in the control group, who did not get any error feedback. It may be concluded that various learners acquire grammar differently or that some target structures do not necessarily require any training.

Grammar Checker

Gorney (2012) discusses factors like email, texting, and Facebook that have caused new words to arise, new grammatical changes to be made, and other changes that are both subtle and obvious. She also emphasizes how technology has increased the speed at which messages can be sent, which has led to a change in grammar usage. However, according to her argument, the rise of technology has reduced the beauty of language, which may be unprofessional and may even lead to a decline in communication between people. In general, the "texting culture" that is emerging emphasizes speed and convenience at the expense of using proper grammar while sending messages.

With this, the development of technology also brought about the language checker. A grammar checker deals with errors that can be detected in contexts that are larger than the word and construction errors, while a spell checker corrects individual text words. Hartley and Tynjala (2001) add that the spelling checker prompts the user to review individual words with incorrect spelling by immediately underlining the words with a wavy red line as an indicator of misspelled words (as cited by Radi, 2015). Additionally, graphical convention violations, soft lowercase errors, and punctuation errors were also handled. The technology can detect the overuse of a word or phrase, extended phrases, and words used out of context, such as "four examples," among other things. In light of this, an online grammar checker can spot more than 300 different types of writing errors and has a number of advantages, including the following: a) saving teachers' time (Bailey & Lee, 2020); b) improving writing quality and engagement (Gauthier, 2013); c) boosting students' motivation and confidence (Potter & Fuller, 2008); d) giving students scaffolded feedback (Bailey & Lee, 2020); and e) lowering writing anxiety that AbuSeileek (2009) contends as he stated that the ability to receive guidance on an individual basis lowers anxiety and fosters a more laid-back learning environment.

However, learners in the twenty-first century have free access to these online language checkers. This has also been made available and utilized on tablets, smartphones, computers, and other tech devices. Grammarly, Ginger Software, QuillBot, SpellCheck Plus, and Turnitin are a few examples of current online language checkers.

According to Street (2013), these modifications have made computer literacy skills more accessible to include interactions and communications through social activities and practices, and language literacy acquisition differs from computer literacy acquisition in terms of achievement and learning development. Sinclair (2010) underlines that because they are so unsure of their own spelling and grammar, many students place their reliance on spelling and grammar checkers. Furthermore, some researchers, according to Olsen and Williams (2004), have researched how much individuals rely on the small, wavy red and green lines in Microsoft documents. They discovered that, while paying attention to what is defined by the lines enhances the quality of bad writers, it makes strong authors worse because they begin to rely entirely on spelling and grammar checkers, neglecting their own intuition.

On the other hand, Potter and Fuller (2008) uncovered the use of a grammar checker tool, taking grammar outside of the textbook and into each student's writing experience. In light of their findings, the students became more concerned about the grammar checker's consequences. Their motivation to use their understanding of the particular grammar units increased, as did their level of interest. It was also mentioned that the usage of English grammar checkers by high school students boosted students' motivation, engagement, confidence in grammatical rules, and level of English language proficiency.

Countless programs have been created to assist language learners in becoming more fluent in their chosen language due to technology's rapid development. An innovative, effective, and powerful instrument for technology-enhanced learning is now available thanks to the Internet. According to AbuSeileek (2009), computer-based methods are better than non-computer-based approaches because they offer more feedback and deliver more tailored content, making it simpler for each learner to comprehend it at their own pace.

In summary, there is relatively sparse research on grammar checkers and how they can help develop grammar skills. Moreover, most reviewed literature is dominated by qualitative studies, and quantitative studies about the role of online grammar checkers in the development of grammar skills in academic discourse are lacking, which this research aims to provide. To look at grammar checkers in the context of developing grammatical skills among senior high school students, further research is required in this area. Grammar checkers have been shown through the aforementioned studies to assist learners in understanding their grammatical errors and learning how to prevent them. However, additional study is necessary to determine how students might use grammar checkers without compromising their knowledge of grammar and its rules.

Role of Grammar Checkers on Grammar Accuracy

Thanks to technological advancements, English language learners can now easily access free online grammar checkers like Grammarly, SpellcheckPlus, and Ginger Software. Turnitin is a new technology that lets students review embedded input from professors on their writing in addition to auto-generated feedback from the system. These grammar checkers are designed to identify grammatical mistakes in student essays and give users immediate, automatic feedback. One useful benefit of automatic, timely feedback is that it eases the grading burden on teachers, which helps maintain consistency in students' grades (Frost et al., 2021). Cotos (2011) found the strength of automated feedback in "*its individualization, time, and cost-effectiveness*" (p. 421). As students became more aware of grammatical faults in their writing, the researcher theorized that automatic feedback could motivate them to write better.

Few studies have examined the effectiveness of grammar checkers, despite the fact that English grammar checkers are constantly being developed. Additionally, conflicting findings from previous research were found on the impact of grammar checkers on student writing errors (Avila et al., 2021; Perdana and Farida, 2019; Pratama, 2021; Yang, 2018). Although using a grammar checker enhanced students' writings' grammatical accuracy, there is not much research that has been done regarding grammar checkers conducted at St. Dominic College of Asia in Cavite, Philippines.

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers used an experimental research design. Ary et al. (2018) state that experimental research design enables researchers to estimate the effect of an affected treatment. Experimental research can be done in the laboratory, in the classroom, and in the field. A researcher chooses the design to determine the validity of the conclusions that can be drawn from the study. This study uses an experimental design in the form of an independent measure design using a quantitative approach. This approach was used to see how well students can check their own grammar using and without online grammar checkers.

Research Sample and Population

This study was conducted at the Senior High School Department of St. Dominic College of Asia. The whole SHS population, consisting of students in grades 11 and 12, was chosen to be the respondents. The whole senior high school population has a total of three hundred forty-four (344) students divided into twelve (12) sections, subdivided into six (6) sections for each grade level, varying with different senior high school strands such as Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Strand (STEM); Humanities and Social Sciences Strand (HUMSS); Accounting, Business, and Management Strand (ABM); and Technical-Vocational Livelihood Track (TVL).

The researchers aimed to acquire responses from the entire SHS unit; however, the study faced some limitations in its sample size. These limitations were mainly caused by the institutions' learning modalities offered during the academic year, which were conducted through a combination of full home-based learning and modified face-to-face learning. After gathering the students' academic e-mail accounts from officials of the office of student affairs and reaching out to the students enrolled under the modified face-to-face learning modality, aiming for a wider number of responses, only two hundred thirty-two (232) respondents submitted their responses for this study. From this number, only 42 were identified who are not using online grammar checkers, so to have an equal number for each experimental and control group, the researchers also took 42 students who are using online grammar checkers. The researchers chose these respondents as they are evidently utilizing technology in learning and acquiring knowledge, which will evaluate the online grammar checkers effectiveness in developing the respondents' English grammar skills.

Research Sampling Procedures

The researchers chose convenience sampling as the sampling method for this study, wherein the respondents are chosen to benefit from the survey. Furthermore, it is more efficient for the study to be conducted primarily in its institution as its main beneficiary and in a nearby location with less formal paperwork during the current health crisis. Moreover, this study only focuses on identifying various grammar checkers to evaluate their frequency of use, which grammar skills are addressed when checking grammar, and comprehending the perception of the qualities of the online grammar checkers towards the students' learning development in English grammar. In light of these, the researchers purposefully asked the respondents which online grammar checker they use.

If they answered that they do not use any online grammar checkers, their responses will automatically be directed to submit their Google Form. Hence, all respondents that participated in the survey satisfy the criteria needed for the fulfillment of this study.

Data Gathering Instruments

The data gathering instrument used in this study is a mixed-type survey questionnaire formulated by the researchers. This questionnaire contains different questions intended to gain responses and collect numerical data that can be used for statistical analysis, which helped the researchers conduct this study. The contents of the survey questionnaire are based on questions related to the study that helped the researchers gather the needed data. The survey questionnaire was done via Google Forms, which consists of the following:

- The first section contains various close-ended multiple-choice statements and Likert scales that aim to identify and evaluate various grammar tools pertaining to their frequency of use, grammar skills addressed, and perception towards their quality, which aim to answer the first and second statements of the problem.
- The second section contains a task-based question, which is a paragraph correction exercise using specific online grammar tools that aims to assist in answering the first statement of the problem.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researchers conducted a survey questionnaire. These survey questionnaires were formulated to efficiently gather the data needed for this study and fit the respondents' schedules wherein as students enrolled under the Modified Face-to-Face Learning modality, they have an alternating schedule where they have a week of face-to-face learning and a week of full home-based learning. The survey questionnaires were disseminated through Google Forms and sent via the respondents' respective academic e-mail accounts. Furthermore, since the researchers gathered the students' academic e-mail accounts, the researchers stated a brief reminder in the survey questionnaires in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, giving an assurance to the respondents that all personal information and gathered data are strictly kept confidential between the researchers for this study only.

The researchers adapted a Likert scale to measure respondents' attitudes toward a particular question or statement within the survey. In this study, they used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the interval of frequency classification and level of agreement. Furthermore, frequency and percentage were used to identify the number of errors, while a t-test was used to determine the significant difference between the control and experimental groups of students.

Results and Discussion

Statement of the Problem 1. *What is the level of perception of using online grammar checkers among Senior High School students?*

Table 1 shows the students' perceptions towards the qualities of various online grammar checkers, wherein all statements are in the mid-point "good," which shows the neutrality of their opinion.

However, the overall mean also shows that the majority of the qualities of online grammar checkers are interpreted as "good" by the students.

Table 1. Students' perception of the qualities of online grammar checkers

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The software has a user-friendly interface, which is easy to use.	3.91	Good
2. The software uses language that is simple and easy to understand.	3.98	Good
3. The software runs without interruptions or problems that needs assistance.	3.44	Good
4. The software increases willingness in usage for next time use.	3.77	Good
5. The software is recommendable to be used by others.	3.93	Good
6. The software can be accessed in any device, and even in regular accounts.	4.06	Good
7. The software ensures minimal or fewer errors in grammar, which makes the paper ready for publication.	3.88	Good
8. The software can detect all errors. It can even find mistakes that I did not notice at first.	3.78	Good
9. The software allows me to think and decide on appropriate suggestions through the Accept or Dismiss options.	3.99	Good
10. The software allows me to apply what I learned from the online grammar tools to my other writing activities.	3.93	Good
11. The software helps me evaluate my own writing progress by discovering my strengths and weaknesses in grammar.	3.98	Good
12. The software educates me about rules in grammar through detailed explanations as to why a correction is suggested.	3.83	Good
13. The software helps improve my vocabulary and word count by suggesting alternatives without changing the context of the matter.	3.96	Good
14. The software adheres to universal grammar rules observed by professional institutions and writers.	3.90	Good
15. The software helps improve my grammar and writing skills with less human assistance.	3.84	Good

Legend: 1.00-1.80 - Very Poor; 1.81-2.60 - Poor; 2.61-3.40 - Fair; 3.41-4.20 - Good; 4.21-5.00 - Very Good

The characteristics that are considered good qualities of online grammar checkers are:

- User-friendly – it is easy to use and is well-designed.
- Uses simple and understandable language.

- Non-human dependent where it runs without interruptions or problems that need assistance.
- Increases willingness in usage.
- Recommendable
- Accessible on any device, and even in regular accounts – can be used in either computer or mobile phone, even without creating a premium or purchased account.
- Ensures minimal grammatical errors, producing a publication-ready output.
- Detects overlooked grammatical errors where it can even find mistakes that were not noticed by the students at first.
- Allows critical thinking of appropriate grammar suggestions through the Accept or Dismiss options.
- Allows applied learning from the online grammar checker to writing activities where it allows to apply what the students learned from the online grammar checkers to other writing activities.
- Helps evaluate writing progress by discovering strengths and weaknesses in grammar.
- Educates grammar rules through detailed explanations of grammar correction suggestions.
- Enhances vocabulary and word count by suggesting alternatives without changing the context of the matter or written output.
- Adheres to universal grammar rules observed by professional institutions and writers.
- Improves grammar and writing skills with less human assistance.

Statement of the Problem 2. *What errors are detected in checking grammar in written texts?*

Table 2. Errors detected by experimental and control groups

Errors	Frequency		Percentage	
	Control	Experimental	Control	Experimental
ERROR 1 Contraction	9	4	22.50%	10.00%
ERROR 2 Punctuation: Period	33	23	82.50%	57.50%
ERROR 3 Verb Tense	4	7	10.00%	17.50%
ERROR 4 Spelling	6	0	15.00%	0.00%
ERROR 5 Adjective	7	10	17.50%	25.00%
ERROR 6 Punctuation: Comma	8	14	20.00%	35.00%
ERROR 7 Parallelism / Verb	6	8	15.00%	20.00%
ERROR 8 Pronoun	4	13	10.00%	32.50%
ERROR 9 Misplaced Modifier	27	26	67.50%	65.00%
ERROR 10 Preposition	16	1	40.00%	2.50%
TOTAL	120	106	30.00%	26.50%

Table 2 shows the areas in grammar that students who do not use online grammar checkers can identify and fix (control group) and the areas in grammar that online grammar checkers can identify and fix (experimental group). In terms of errors detected, it shows that the area of grammar that can be detected the most by the control group is punctuation (33), followed by misplaced modifiers (27), and prepositions (16). However, the errors that can be detected the most by online grammar checkers are misplaced modifiers (26), followed by prepositions (23), and punctuation (14). It can be noticed that both groups have the same highest number of errors detected in punctuation and preposition, which are common errors detected by most human editors and online grammar checkers.

Statement of the Problem 3. *Is there a significant difference between the control group and experimental group in terms of checking grammar in written texts?*

The table below shows that in terms of the total number of errors detected, it can be seen that the control group was able to detect 120 errors, which is a little higher than the experimental group with 106 errors. However, the results did not create a significant difference between control and experimental groups in detecting grammar errors. Nonetheless, students who do not use online grammar checkers (control group) can identify and fix more errors than those students who use online grammar checkers with regular or free accounts (experimental group).

Table 3. Significant difference of control and experimental groups towards grammar checking

Groups	N	Total No. of Errors	t stat	p-value	Interpretation
Control	42	120	0.331	0.372	Not Significant
Experimental	42	106			

Statement of the Problem 4. *What instructional guidelines can be proposed based on the result of this study?*

Based on the result of the study, the researchers therefore recommend the following guidelines to help students and teachers in using online grammar checkers. Online grammar checkers can have advantages in terms of convenience, free usage, and time. However, students and teachers should consider the following:

Guidelines for Students:

- Students should recognize the weaknesses of the grammar checkers. Most of these tools are not always accurate or reliable and also have limitations, especially for free versions. There are even studies that show that most online grammar checkers cannot detect all common errors in grammar, like punctuation, prepositions, articles, voice, and idioms.
- Students should always think that written English may not always be written correctly. Even native English speakers sometimes write ungrammatical texts. If it is an academic paper, students should first ask their paper adviser, teacher, or school handbook, if there is one, about the guidelines or areas in grammar that they should consider because there is no standard guideline for grammar editing. It may depend on the institution or research committee.

- Students should understand that aside from the fact that online grammar checkers may not always be available due to internet disruption, most online grammar checkers cannot find and fix all the common errors, so students should know how to edit their own work manually. Students should never stop learning about grammar because writing is a lifelong process. So, knowing how to check grammar on their own is the quickest way to improve their credibility with their target audience.
- Students should be aware that, even after making minor edits, the grammar checker may not agree a sentence they have accepted as error-free in a given text if it was identified by the checker initially. This emphasizes how crucial it is that students carefully evaluate any recommendations the checker may provide.
- To make sure the explanation offered for the problem fits the situation, students should also pause to think about it or take note of it. For instance, occasionally the grammar checker incorrectly flags a whole sentence as a fragment.
- Students can control the use of grammar checkers without them being controlled by the checkers. They can change the settings of the grammar checker to suit their needs. For example, in Microsoft Word, users can navigate to the "Tools" menu, choose "Options," click "Spelling and Grammar," and select the settings they want to use while their grammar checker scans their writing. Writing styles vary in terms of the kinds of words they use and the quantity of suggestions they make. Examples of these choices are gender-specific words and passive voice. They can also ask the grammar checker to ignore internet addresses or always recommend corrections. Students should carefully consider the settings and select the ones that best fit their needs as writers, making any necessary adjustments to their spelling and punctuation.
- Students should consider the available time for editing. Although using an online checker can save editing time with just a few clicks correcting all possible mistakes, if there is enough time before the deadline, students should consider correcting the grammar errors by themselves or look for an editor or grammarian.
- Students can use both tools—human editing and online editing—to check their grammar to ensure the best overall revision.
- Students should understand that grammar checkers are not a replacement for a human editor. Human editors are still better because they can do critical thinking or analysis, something that online grammar checkers cannot. Only human editors and proofreaders can enhance the following aspects:
 - ◇ **Context:** Online grammar checkers cannot recognize context. Grammar checkers merely match patterns derived from mechanical computations and offer suggestions with no understanding of context because online grammar checkers do not think.
 - ◇ **Readability:** Depending on whether you are working on a business proposal, technical article, or college application essay, you need to use a different vocabulary and style.
 - ◇ **Flow and Sentence Combining:** Human editors combine disparate or separate ideas into coherent, well-connected sentences. This requires a native command of the English language and an understanding of the author's intentions.

- ◇ **Word Count:** There are word count limitations for many sorts of writing. Parts of the text that are unnecessary can be found and eliminated with the aid of an objective viewpoint on the context and purpose of the manuscript.
- ◇ **Term Usage and Consistency:** Theses and dissertations are full of references to various literature articles, all of which come from different sources. Additionally, technical terms may have different usages than normal writing. Human editors know not only what these technical terms mean; they also know when and how to apply them.

Guidelines for Faculty:

The use of an online grammar checker may not always be helpful to all students. Students with low proficiency can be easily fooled by inaccurate feedback from the grammar checker. So, teachers should do something to assist the students during the process of revising their written papers.

- Teachers must give extra guidance or engage students in in-class activities to help them respond appropriately to feedback from grammar checkers that is not accurate.
- Teachers should advise their students to utilize grammar checkers to verify the correctness of their early drafts of writing by using them as a preparatory tool. Students' attention may be drawn to the use of proper grammar during the writing process by an early grammar check.
- Teachers may encourage students to list particular areas for criticism, such as what they are unsure of. Asking why they are unsure about a sentence, what rules they know about the specific grammar structure, if they assessed a reference book, and if they can demonstrate the page so the teacher can seek out the rules together are just a few of the questions they can use. Teachers can gain a great deal of insight into the minds of their students, which will be useful when assisting each individual kid. However, educators need to be mindful of how much time they are devoting to these concerns. Students may become frustrated if they are asked to consider each and every mistake in depth, as is understandable. More questioning is a good idea for structures that adhere to a set of rules more strictly, such as verb tenses or gerunds vs. participles.
- The teacher can find out where the children had trouble choosing a language. Sometimes students fail to recognize a sentence they think might be wrong because they genuinely think they have written it in proper English. Instructors can question students about their decision-making process by asking them to show where they had to work hard. By asking them questions like "*Why was this a hard choice? How else were you thinking of saying it? What made you choose this way?*" they can either congratulate students on making the right decision and reinforce it, or they can correct them and possibly teach them a trick for making a good decision the next time (e.g., a mnemonic device, a great page in your preferred reference book).

- Errors classified as "high gravity" or those that actually impede pupils' comprehension can be identified by the teacher. Instructors can collaborate with students to determine how and why their intended meaning is being obscured by the sentence structure or word choice. The teacher can provide students with the terminology they need to articulate their ideas grammatically once they have sufficiently explained them for the teacher to understand.
- Together with the students, the teacher can assist through error correction, assisting the learner in comprehending and applying the rules, identifying a few more situations of the same type of error, and then allowing the students to attempt fixing the errors using the resource. The teacher may proceed on to the next sort of problem when the students are comfortable enough to identify and fix that one.
- The teacher can ask students to use supplementary materials like a printed or online dictionary, which include information about grammar and vocabulary.
- Teachers can find grammar checkers also useful to help students develop their digital literacy, since some grammar checkers with premium account can function as plagiarism checkers.
- Teachers can use their authority to inform the developers of grammar checkers to enhance their services like the technical capability of error detection and accuracy of feedback.

Conclusions

The results presented relatively positive perceptions, where the majority of the students perceive that online grammar checkers have good qualities and can be useful in editing their written academic texts. This shows that most online checkers adhere to the universal grammar rules recognized by authors and professional institutions, as it correlates with Lev Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development. Thus, the term "professional institutions and writers" is equivalent to "more knowledgeable others" or "more advanced peers," which describes the scope of achievement between what a learner can achieve on their own and what they can achieve with assistance from others. Given that the study discovered that learners perceive online grammar as having "good" qualities and that the attributes are beneficial to their learning, these do not serve as a substitute for a professional who teaches and explains technical grammatical rules; rather, they only assist in automating the checking of grammar and determining grammar skills. Nonetheless, it is critical to realize that grammar checkers do not serve as a substitute for a human editor. Several of these instruments lack perfection. They do not replace critical thinking; rather, they only assist in automating a fundamental process.

However, although the difference between the control group and the experimental group is slightly higher, it still shows that there is no significant difference in error rates for both groups of students. But it is possible that students who do not use online grammar checkers can identify and fix more errors than online grammar checkers, which were used by students with regular or free accounts. The result could have been different if students who use online grammar checkers used premium accounts, which have the advantage of correcting more advanced errors that other grammar checkers with regular or free accounts would miss.

This has been one of the limitations of the study, where full features of the online grammar checkers were not applied since most students would not be able to afford to pay for premium accounts. Also, the difference in error rates between the control and experimental groups shows the performance of human editors versus the performance of digital editors like Grammarly and QuillBot, which may not possess common variables or qualities.

The result also assumes that while the majority of SHS students have a positive perception of using online grammar checkers, it also shows that a large proportion of the students have high proficiency in grammar since they can identify and fix errors in grammar even without the use of online grammar checkers. Students believed that online grammar checkers did not require human assistance and that they could learn on their own, exhibiting the traits of self-directed learning, just as they perceived the qualities of the grammar checkers characterized in the survey.

The new generation of students has grown up with technology and has intimate knowledge of the benefits of using online tools. Although they are not dependent on them, they show a balanced skill in using both grammar tools. With this in mind, it shows that students can decide which tool is more appropriate to use depending on the context and necessity.

Recommendations

Since this research paper is generally focused on the evaluation of online grammar checkers pertaining to how a grammar skill is developed through measuring the frequency of use, perception towards the quality of the online grammar tool, and the grammar skills addressed, on the basis of the present study, the researchers would like to recommend the following:

For researchers. It is recommended to research and investigate further and wider scopes of evaluating how a grammar tool can help develop English grammar skills. More so, research other factors that may affect the development of grammar skills with the integration of online grammar tools. In addition, it is also recommended to expand the scope of respondents to other levels, such as junior high school students, higher education students, and even professionals, to further study the development of English grammar skills.

For further research. It is recommended that this study be done fully in a face-to-face setting to formally gather data and to instantly track if a respondent answered the survey questionnaires. Due to limitations in time and resources, the initial approach in this study was unable to be satisfactory. Therefore, the researchers highly suggest that future researchers enhance or modify the approach to this study to investigate the phenomenon further. Using more open-ended and closed-ended questions may help future research elaborate on the interconnection of online grammar tools and the development of English grammar skills.

For professional teachers. Though online grammar checkers should not be taken as a substitute for human editors, it is recommended that teachers consider using them to double-check written output both for themselves and their students, as these online grammar checkers can also detect grammatical errors that may have been overlooked by teachers.

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